

Metrological validation of a deep learning pipeline for in-line detection and dimensional quantification of three-dimensional surface defects

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ABSTRACT

Defect detection is critical in manufacturing processes such as casting, machining, and additive manufacturing, where imperfections can impair part functionality and reliability. This work proposes a deep learning-based methodology for the detection and dimensional inspection of three-dimensional surface defects. The approach integrates deep learning trained on pre-labelled data and applied to two-dimensional deviation maps derived from laser-based measurements, and a skeletonization algorithm to estimate defect dimensions. Accuracy is ensured by metrological validation using reference measurements from a multisensor coordinate measuring machine. Applied to die-cast components, the framework demonstrates robust performance, offering a reliable tool for integration into real-world quality control workflows.

1. Introduction

In the industrial manufacturing sector, quality control plays a crucial role in ensuring the functionality, safety, and reliability of products [1, 2]. In high-volume production processes, the presence of small and complex three-dimensional (3D) surface defects, also known as geometrical imperfections, can significantly compromise the mechanical integrity and functional performance of the produced parts, thereby altering their quality, aesthetic, and safety [3]. Machine vision systems (MVS) for automated visual inspection are now widely deployed in-line and often serve as the primary screening method for detecting defects [4]. They pre-select parts and pass ambiguous cases to trained operators for final acceptance or rework decisions. The effectiveness of MVS depends critically on illumination design and acquisition geometry, which govern the visibility of defects and, consequently, the downstream detection performance for both machines and humans. In this context, human visual inspection (HVI) is nowadays considered in a complementary role to MVS, rather than as a standalone solution. Traditionally, the inspection of geometrical imperfections on manufactured surfaces [5] is carried out through HVI performed by trained operators, often supported by simple contact or optical measuring tools, and characterised by the adoption of sensorial strategies in the analysis process [4]. Baudet et al [6]. emphasise the importance of structured HVI tools, proposing a type of sensorial analysis that classifies surface anomalies using a specified vocabulary and tables (i.e., criteria/level table,

tree-like presentation table, and indexed table). This approach aims to reduce operator subjectivity and improve reproducibility by standardizing descriptors such as marks, pollution, and heterogeneity, and linking them to measurable attributes like contrast or depth, uniquely attributed to the identified anomalies. Nakajima et al [7]. explore the limitations of HVI when utilising peripheral vision, focusing on how the shape of defects may affect detection performance. Specifically, they evaluated twelve subjects based on experimental factors such as defect shapes, defect locations, and defect characteristics (i.e., luminance contrast between the defect and the inspection surface and size). They found that line-shaped defects are more complex to detect compared to geometric shapes like circles, triangles, or squares, regardless of contrast or size. Despite being a widely adopted approach, HVI's inherent operators' subjectivity and susceptibility to fatigue have driven the development of automated visual inspection systems. In line with the above, recent work explores the role of machine vision systems in industrial inspection in contexts where human judgment is still part of the loop. Tjolleng et al [8]. propose a human-friendly visual inspection method for detecting defects on painted vehicle bodies. The study introduces a new inspection device that projects bright-dark linear stripes to reveal surface irregularities, thereby improving defect visibility. The authors compared the obtained results with a conventional lighting method: the new system significantly reduced eye fatigue and significantly increased defect detectability (92.1 % as opposed to 73.4 %). In [9,10] the importance of the correct design of the illumination and

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image acquisition setup is highlighted, enhancing visibility of surface imperfection for both human operators and inspection machines. In [9], the authors discuss how lighting and wavelength selection directly affect defect detectability, arguing that image quality starts with human-centred illumination strategies. In [10], camera placement and illumination type (bright/dark field) appear to influence the ability of both human and machine observers to detect surface defects.

As part of the ongoing digital transformation, machine learning (ML) techniques have shown high effectiveness in identifying surface defects in combination with automated visual inspection systems. Numerous studies have specifically explored the use of deep learning architectures to enhance detection performance [11–13]. Several reviews have been conducted to identify the advantages and limitations of these methods compared to traditional ones. Czimmermann et al. [14] provide a comprehensive survey of automated visual inspection techniques, highlighting the growing role of ML and surface texture analysis in defect classification. They discuss low- and high-level image processing approaches, comparing traditional statistical methods, structural and filter-based methods, and ML approaches. In their review, Gao et al. [15] illustrate the most recent vision-based defect recognition strategies, dividing them into designed-feature (e.g., statistical-based) and learned-feature-based (e.g., deep learning architectures) methods. Their research emphasizes the transition from handcrafted feature extraction to data-driven models and highlights the challenges of deploying such systems in real-world manufacturing, including the need for large, labelled datasets, and high computational efficiency. Among manufacturing domains, the ML-based detection and monitoring of surface defects in additive manufacturing provides a significant example, widely studied in the literature. For the measurement of microscale surface impurities in additive manufacturing processes, various strategies in tandem with ML models have been proposed for inspection in-situ, as comprehensively reviewed in [16]. Prior studies have detected microscale surface imperfections in laser powder bed fusion (PBF-LB) using light scattering and unsupervised machine learning [17], have addressed surface defect prediction in injection moulding by applying transfer learning (TL) [18], have developed a surrogate model for detecting keyhole pores in PBF-LB, combining melt pool imaging with X-Ray Computed Tomography (CT) validation [19], and have predicted spatter-related porosities using off-axis long-exposure imaging and compared analytical and ML-based methods, both trained with data aligned to post-process CT measurements [20].

1.1. ML-driven inspection in die casting

Recent research has increasingly adopted ML-driven approaches to improve surface defect detection specifically in die-cast applications. Several approaches integrate ML, computer vision, and process analytics to address the challenges posed by complex manufacturing conditions, variability, and the need for real-time monitoring. Several studies have investigated the application of machine learning models trained on process data to predict surface or internal defects [21–23]. These studies demonstrated how neural networks and supervised learning methods can map process parameters (such as temperature, velocity, or pressure) to defect occurrence or mechanical properties like tensile strength. In particular, Gellrich et al [23], employed transfer learning to enhance robustness across various production conditions in aluminium gravity die casting. Other studies have focused on combining imaging methods with deep learning (DL) to perform automated inspections [24,25]. In particular, these studies used convolutional neural networks (CNNs) trained on CT and metallographic images to detect casting defects and extract microstructural properties. Mohammed et al [26], applied sparse CNNs and scan-to-CAD alignment to localise burrs and estimate their dimensions, achieving results comparable to CT scans. These vision-based methods demonstrate high accuracy in detecting surface anomalies, even in noisy or incomplete imaging conditions. Zhang et al [27], applied a similar strategy to continuous casting, predicting slag

inclusions using ML and time-series sensor data. They employed several ML algorithmic solutions, and their designed pipeline showed strong performance despite imbalanced data distribution, reinforcing the effectiveness of well-tuned classification algorithms. These studies show how combining ML-based methods and visual inspection systems can lead to more effective and reliable defect detection in die casting applications. However, the lack of standardized protocols for data acquisition and evaluation still represents a barrier to broader industrial adoption.

1.2. Research motivation and contents

High-volume manufacturing increasingly mandates traceable, real-time inspection, ensuring that quality data can be trusted, compared across plants, and fed directly back to process control. Despite the promising performance in classification and defect detection, ML approaches often lack traceability and rarely address the accuracy of the measurements obtained [28]. In particular, the use of ML in defect detection often carries three critical limitations: a) CNNs are often trained on datasets labelled via a non-traceable HVI methodology, which introduces errors at both training and validation stages, or on simulated datasets that may not fully capture the complexity and variability of real surface defects, thus limiting the generalizability of the trained models; b) the output of these models is usually limited to a binary classification (i.e., defective versus non-defective components), with no dimensional quantification of the detected defects; c) most systems are not ready for use in-line. Accordingly, the proposed study is driven by the need for a metrologically validated DL-based methodology that couples defect detection and classification with quantitative dimensional assessment, enabling data-driven process control and reducing downstream rework and scrap in die-cast production. Die-cast automotive components have been selected as the test case for this study, due to their industrial relevance and the occurrence of surface defects. However, the proposed inspection pipeline is designed to be broadly applicable across various manufacturing processes where imperfections exhibit a 3D morphology, provided that the detector is re-trained or fine-tuned on representative, process-specific defect data. The proposed pipeline is well-suited for seamless integration into in-line quality control workflows, enabling real-time defect quantification and providing decision support for experienced operators. The study addresses the following research questions:

1. How can 3D acquisitions be used consistently within 2D DL-based pipelines?
2. How can defect dimensions (e.g., length, width) be derived from 2D deviation maps?
3. How should such measurements be validated and compared against traceable references?

Although most types of defects feature a 3D conformation, the literature largely frames inspection as a 2D vision task, with limited attention to 3D descriptors; most studies operate on 2D projections/images, and rigorous 3D quantification remains uncommon. In this work, the problem is partially addressed by acquiring 3D dense point clouds of the defective regions rather than conventional images; this data is then converted into 2D deviation maps by projecting point-to-reference distances onto a plane. It is worth pointing out that this method preserves the defects footprint, while the vertical morphology is reduced to colour intensity.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the proposed methodology, the selected case study, the experimental setups used for data acquisition, and the proposed pipeline for data processing and analysis. Section 3 presents the experimental results obtained on the automotive die-cast parts, including defect detection using the trained CNN, as well as dimensional quantification through the skeletonization algorithm. Finally, Section 4 discusses the results obtained and Section 5

highlights industrial implications, concluding with future research directions.

2. Materials and methods

The proposed methodology adopts a supervised DL approach with transfer learning: a convolutional detector is trained on pre-labelled images to localise defects. As the method is supervised and relies on labelled data, the limitations of a mid-sized dataset are mitigated via transfer learning, initialising the detector from pre-trained weights and then fine-tuning so that generic visual features are adapted to die-casting defect morphology, reducing labelling effort and improving generalisation. Specifically, the model is applied to deviation maps, which are generated by comparing 3D point cloud data acquired via laser triangulation on sample parts to high-resolution scan data of a master part. After registration to a common coordinate frame, the deviation maps obtained from the comparison are converted into images. The obtained 2D deviation maps are augmented and adapted to be fed into the CNN model that operates to localise candidate defects. Training of the CNN for the detection of defects and their dimensional quantification is performed on a pre-labelled dataset, which is then augmented to simulate industrial-like conditions. Subsequently, a skeletonization algorithm is applied to the detected regions to extract shape descriptors and estimate the principal dimensions of each defect. The results obtained are then compared to reference measurements collected from an imaging sensor mounted on a multisensor coordinate measuring machine (CMM). The proposed pipeline for defect detection and quantification is shown in Fig. 1.

Details of the selected test case and the type of defects taken into consideration for this study are presented hereafter, as well as the measuring instruments employed, the DL-driven model proposed, the adopted metrics for performance assessment of the CNN training, and the strategy chosen to carry out the reference measurements for defect quantification.

2.1. Selected test case and defect type

As a case study, a sample of aluminium alloy AlSi12 (Fe) cold-chamber die-cast parts for an automotive electrical PCB has been selected. The part is the housing that forms the structural base of the Long-Range Radar Sensor system used in Advanced Driver-Assistance Systems (ADAS) in new-generation cars. Because the housing carries control electronics, even slight geometrical or surface imperfections can compromise assembly, damage cables insulation, trigger electronic failures, and pose safety hazards for workers handling the metal parts during production. Defective parts must therefore be identified and rejected. Accordingly, every component is traditionally inspected by HVI after casting, moulding, slide-grinding, and before packaging [29]. An example part from the batch available for this study is shown in Fig. 2, featuring an approximate total volume of $(78 \times 81 \times 29.4)$ mm.

Local geometrical imperfections can appear in diverse shapes and scales and typically cover only a small portion of the overall surface of a manufactured part. Defects occurring in high-pressure die casting have been comprehensively discussed in the literature [30], and subdivided into a three-level taxonomy based on position/morphology,

Fig. 2. Aluminium die casting component chosen for the evaluation of surface defects.

Fig. 1. Proposed workflow for defect detection and quantification.

metallurgical origin, and other specific characteristics. Within this framework, the present work focuses on the detection of burrs, i.e., raised sharp edges caused by molten aluminium extending beyond the intended die geometry because penetrating into die cracks due to thermal fatigue, generating defects appearing as protrusions on the surface of casting [31]. Such burrs are industrially critical surface defects in high-pressure die casting and have been identified as pivotal contributors to scrap and rework of critical components [32,33]; even small protrusions can hinder assembly, damage wiring, or create handling hazards, which makes their rapid detection and dimensional control a priority in quality assurance workflows. In high-pressure die-cast parts, burrs are also found in correspondence of the geometrical joint lines (Fig. 3). In this study, only these areas were taken into consideration and inspected. The size of these residual burrs on this type of components ranges from 0.4 to 2 mm (Table 1). These are generated during both the moulding and the shearing, and subsequent removal of the sprue and casting attachments from the mould itself.

A systematic naming convention was adopted to uniquely identify each die-cast component and to indicate the number of surface defects detected. Each component was labelled using the format Category-ID-DefectCount, where “Category” refers to the type of component (for example, in this study, HSG for housing), “ID” is a progressive number, and “DefectCount” is the number of defects found on the part. For instance, the label HSG-01–3 identifies the first housing component with three detected defects. This convention will be used in Section 3 to present the results.

2.2. Experimental campaign and point cloud processing

The experimental work was carried out in a temperature- and humidity-controlled laboratory at (20 ± 0.5) °C and (45 ± 10) % respectively. Approximately 90 parts were measured using an articulated arm coordinate measuring machine (AACMM) Nikon MCAX laser-based sensor (Fig. 4(a)). As can be seen in the figure, the parts were fixed on Mitutoyo modular clamping units fastened to a rectangular plate. Two washers, one between the part’s lower face and the support mounted to the plate, the other between the upper support and the part’s top face, were used to improve stability during the measurement. For every measurement, each component’s lateral faces were identified as Sides A, B, C and D, as shown in Fig. 4(b); this convention remained unchanged for all parts throughout the study and it was also maintained for the extraction of the 2D deviation maps, for identification of the defective sides. Each component of the batch was measured once. From this point onwards, the 3D point clouds obtained with the laser triangulation sensor mounted on the AACMM will be identified as “test” point clouds.

The obtained scans were compared to a point cloud obtained from a “master” defect-free part using a high-resolution optical laser triangulation-based in-line industrial setup, developed in previous work [29,32,33]. This system consists of a telecentric lens camera for capturing the top surface of the parts, and four laser triangulators for

measuring the sides. The part is placed on a turntable, a centring mask guarantees repeatable positioning, and an industrial robot handles pick-and-place. The master point cloud presented an average point-to-point spacing equal to 10 μm and was chosen as a reference because it represented a better digital model of the actual parts than the nominal CAD model. In an industrial setting, a specific master point cloud is required for each nominal component (i.e., generated once from a conforming part and used as the reference geometry), and is fully consistent and in analogy with standard 3D inspection practice. The comparison provided the basis for generating 2D deviation maps, which were used as input to the CNN for defect detection. Table 2 reports both instruments’ specifications.

The test point clouds were first processed by removing inconsistent measured points (i.e., points not representing the four sides of the part) and via filtering operations to eliminate outliers and redundant data. These processes were performed using the commercial software Geomagic Control X, with appropriate settings chosen to maintain any relevant imperfections. Specifically, sampling was performed with a point-to-point spacing of 100 μm , providing visualisation of defects ≥ 1 mm and sufficient detail for smaller imperfections of approximately 0.6 mm; accordingly, the maximum allowable deviation is set to one-tenth of the average point spacing, i.e., 10 μm . After initial processing of the acquired data, the cleaned point clouds were registered to the master point cloud using Matlab in two phases: a) coarse registration using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), which first translated each test point cloud to align its centroid with that of the master; then, a rotation was applied in order to match the first, second and third principal axes of the datasets. This step minimised the risk of local minima due to part symmetry; b) fine registration using the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm, which refined the coarse alignment. After registration, the aligned data were modified to crop out the protruding features at the base of the component, not of interest in this work. To enable CNN-based image analysis, the 3D deviation maps generated, representing local surface height differences between the reference and the target datasets stored as RGB information, were segmented into the four sides of the part. The workflow of point cloud processing, including acquisition, filtering, registration, colour maps generation, and side-wise segmentation steps, is summarised in Fig. 5.

2.3. Point cloud-to-image conversion and data augmentation

The deviation maps extracted from each side were projected onto assigned planes (i.e., each pair of faces is aligned to their projection planes, Side 1 \rightarrow XZ, Side 2 \rightarrow YZ; Side 3 \rightarrow XZ, Side 4 \rightarrow YZ, as shown in Fig. 6(a)), and converted into 2D images to be fed into the CNN architecture (Fig. 6(b)). All maps were normalized to ensure consistent interpretation by the CNN model and encoded with colourmap. For each face in a component, points were binned onto a 2D grid and the median deviation in each cell was calculated, corresponding to the image pixel intensity. Each map was then independently normalized by min–max scaling, bringing all values into [0,1]. Empty cells were excluded by the calculation. Values near the per-map minimum were rendered in blue, progressively larger deviations shifted to warmer colours, with the per-map maximum saturated to red. Because scaling is performed per map, absolute colours are not directly comparable across components/faces; the colormap is fixed, but the dynamic range is image-specific. Cells with no points were handled via a separate binary mask and rendered in black. As a result, from the 92 components available for this study, a dataset of 368 images was built (i.e., 87 capturing defects, and 281 defect-free). It is worth pointing out that a balancing operation of the dataset was needed to prevent the network from over-fitting to the majority class and misclassifying instances [34]. This strategy ensures that the model learns features from both classes equally, improving its ability to detect defects effectively. For this reason, the number of images used was reduced, with a slight bias towards those presenting defects: the final set contained 85 “defective” and 75 “non-defective”

Fig. 3. Example of a defect found in the correspondence of the geometrical joint lines between the moving parts of the die-casting mould (in green) and the casting connection (highlighted in the yellow square).

Table 1
Selected type of defect.

Type of defect (ISO 8785:1998)	Description	Approx. size

* Image captured with a telecentric camera at $0.50 \times$ magnification

Fig. 4. Measurement set-up for optical measurements: (a) example of a component measured with the AACMM Nikon MCAx laser triangulation sensor, fixed on a rectangular plate through modular clamping units (supplied by Mitutoyo); (b) naming convention for each component's side.

Table 2
Systems specifications.

	Technology	Average point-to-point sampling	Accuracy of the laser sensor, as stated by the manufacturer	Point count
<i>In-line optical setup</i>	Laser-based	10 μm	$\pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$	approx. 1100,000
AACMM Nikon MCAx	Laser-based	100 μm	$\pm 10 \mu\text{m}$	approx. 800,000

images. The initial distinction and subdivision were performed manually through visual assessment.

The obtained dataset was uploaded into the platform Roboflow [35], to perform several operations of data preparation before training the CNN. First, in order to simulate the implementation of the pipeline in an in-line inspection process, the dataset was augmented in the same platform by varying some conditions, such as exposure $\pm 10\%$, brightness $\pm 15\%$, saturation $\pm 15\%$, and rotation $\pm 5^\circ$. The strategy reflected the hypothesis that a real implementation will be highly repeatable and any variation in the output images will be limited to mild changes in brightness, contrast, part alignment, or rotation (e.g., from imperfect fixturing). From the 160 originals (i.e., 85 “defective” and 75 “non-defective” images), additional augmented images were generated to emulate in-line variability. A working subset was then selected so that the overall dataset comprised 400 images. A subset corresponding to 20% of the defect-containing images was annotated using an assisted labelling tool, allowing imperfections to be identified through rectangular bounding boxes (i.e., a rectangle that encloses an object or a region of interest). The rest of the images (both with or without visible defects) were left unchanged. All images were resized to 640×640 pixels (as it is

shown in Fig. 6(c)) to match the detector input; resizing was performed without padding (i.e., aspect ratio may change). Dimensional estimates were then computed in metric units by skeletonizing the defect mask and converting each pixel step with a pixel-to-mm factor derived from the pre-resize image dimensions (see later Eq. (1)). The sequence of image conversion and dataset preparation including augmentation is summarised in Fig. 7.

2.4. DL-based model for defect detection and dimensional inspection

The network adopted in this work was YOLOv8 (Ultralytics, Python API [36]). To build and evaluate the model correctly, the input data (labelled, augmented, and resized) were split into three independent subsets: a training set for learning the weights, a validation set for tuning parameters and tracking overfitting, and a test set used once at the end for an unbiased performance estimate. Empirical studies report that allocating 70–80% of data for training and 20–30% for validation/testing typically yields favourable generalisation performance of the models, especially in small to mid-sized datasets [37]. Thus, after augmentation, the dataset of 400 images annotated with two classes (defective and non-defective) was further partitioned into training (70%), validation (20%), and test (10%) subsets. Validation and test were drawn exclusively from the original images, while the training split comprised all augmented images together with a subset of originals. No augmented variant of a given original appears in validation or test, and class ratios were preserved across splits. This 70 / 20 / 10 split is a common practice in computer vision and DL, ensuring sufficient data for training while keeping an unseen set for unbiased testing.

After training, the model in its optimal configuration (based on the metrics later discussed in Section 2.4.1) was applied to the unlabelled dataset to perform the detection of defects and their quantification. For each image classified by the model as containing a defect, the analysis proceeded in two phases: a) the bounding box surrounding the defect

Fig. 5. Workflow of phase 1: point cloud processing.

Fig. 6. Conversion from 3D deviation maps to images per each side of the i^{th} measured component: (a) projection of the points onto selected planes (i.e., each pair of faces is aligned to their projection planes), (b) conversion from 3D to 2D maps, and (c) images resizing to 640×640 pixels without padding (aspect ratio may change). Note: non-uniform scaling can distort geometry; metric lengths are obtained from skeletons using a pixel-to-mm conversion factor (Eq. (1)).

was extracted, providing both the location and the approximate dimensions of the defective region; b) from the localised area, a skeletonization algorithm [38] was applied to quantify the extension of the defect. In the first stage, a pixel-to-millimetre scale factor was defined to convert the boxes dimensions into approximate defect sizes. The pixel-to-millimetre conversion factor was calculated as indicated in Eq. (1), where 29.4 mm is the height of each component and 640 pixels is the height resolution of the produced images.

$$\text{Conversion factor} = \frac{29.4 \text{ mm}}{640 \text{ pixels}} = 0.046 \text{ mm} / \text{pixels} \quad (1)$$

Since 29.4 mm is mapped to 640 pixels, vertical distances in the deviation maps scale linearly and can be converted to millimetres with a single constant factor. During the second phase, the skeletonization algorithm started from the binary mask of each detected defect (Fig. 8(a)). The outer contour was re-parameterized by arc length and uniformly sampled every Δs to obtain equally spaced boundary samples (i.e., key points, as shown in Fig. 8(b)). A constrained Voronoi tessellation built from the key points was computed inside the mask as in Fig. 8(c); only Voronoi edges fully contained in the mask were retained. Edges equidistant from the key points on opposite sides of the boundary provided a discrete approximation of the medial axis of the defect (Fig. 8(d)). The resulting medial structure was converted into a one-pixel-wide trace, i.e., the skeleton (Fig. 8(e)), by applying a procedure that thins the topology of the defect while preserving its structure: at each iteration pixels were removed only when their deletion did not change the connectivity of the shape; in this way, the skeleton preserves the topology of the original mask. The algorithm returned the defect's total length in pixels, which was then later converted to millimetres. As final output, labelled images with location, approximate size and length of the detected defects were obtained.

The total length L_{sk} of each detected defect was computed as the sum of the lengths $l_{sk,i}$ of the n skeleton segments that compose it, as indicated in Eq. (2).

$$L_{sk} = \sum_{i=1}^n l_{sk,i} \quad (2)$$

It is worth pointing out that several image processing strategies can be used to retrieve defect length, including geodesic shortest paths within the binary mask, Hough-based line fitting, and more [39]. In practice these approaches either depend on reliable endpoint detection and heavy parameter tuning, are less stable when the contour is rough, mix length with width, and miss branches. For these reasons, skeletonization was chosen as preferred approach in this work: it yields a single centreline, is insensitive to local width, and naturally accounts for branches. The skeletonization step was used primarily for quantification of the defect length L_{sk} ; this length was then benchmarked against measurements obtained with a multisensor CMM, as described in Section 2.5.

Fig. 7. Workflow of phase 2: image conversion and dataset preparation.

Fig. 8. Schematic illustration of the skeletonization algorithm: a) binary mask of the defect; b) uniform arc-length sampling of the outer contour (step Δs), yielding equally spaced key points; c) Voronoi tessellation induced by the same key points; d) medial axis segments obtained as Voronoi edges equidistant from key points on opposite sides of the boundary; e) final one-pixel-wide skeleton after topology-preserving thinning.

2.4.1. Metrics for DL-based model classification performance

The following metrics, solely related to the detection of the defects, were investigated and used as the primary criteria to evaluate the model's performance in classifying images into "defective" and "non-defective". They served as evaluation criteria to identify the most effective training configuration, based on performance observed during both validation and testing phases. Four visual classification possible outcomes, such as True Positive (TP), False Negative (FN), True Negative (TN) and False Positive (FP) can be retrieved from a Confusion Matrix [4]. Generally speaking, the Confusion Matrix is used to provide a class-related overview of prediction performance. Since this work addressed a binary classification problem at the image level (i.e., determining whether an image contains at least one defect), the Confusion Matrix was constructed by evaluating the overall presence of defects in each image, rather than considering individual instances or bounding boxes. A prediction was considered correct if the model's output matched the presence or absence of defects in the image.

The selected prediction metrics are defined as follows [4]:

- True Positive Accuracy (TPA): this metric is commonly identified as Precision. It is the proportion of correctly predicted defect instances among all predicted instances, and it is calculated as reported in Eq. (3), where TP is equal to correctly detected defects, and FP is the number of detected defects that are effectively not present in the images.

$$TPA = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (3)$$

- True Positive Rate (TPR): this metric is commonly identified as Recall. It is the proportion of correctly predicted defect instances among all actual defect instances, and it is calculated from the Confusion Matrix as in Eq. (4), where FN are real defects that have been detected.

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (4)$$

- F Factor: this factor is the harmonic mean of TPA and TPR . It provides a balanced assessment of a model's performance while considering both false positives and false negatives. It is found as reported in Eq. (5).

$$FFactor = 2 \cdot \frac{TPA \cdot TPR}{TPA + TPR} \quad (5)$$

- Mean Average Precision (mAP): It evaluates how well the model detects objects and accurately localises their bounding boxes,

combining *TPA* and *TPR* across different thresholds. It is especially useful in multi-class object detection scenarios. It is calculated as in Eq. (6), where n is the number of classes and AP_i is the average precision for the i^{th} class, calculated as the area under the Precision-Recall curve for a specific class $\int_0^1 P(r)dr$, with $P(r)$ precision at recall r .

$$mAP = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n AP_i \quad (6)$$

- **Detection Success Rate (DSR):** this metric is also identified as Accuracy. It is the proportion of correct predictions over the total number of cases; it provides a general indication of the model's ability to correctly classify both defective and non-defective images, therefore ultimately capturing the accuracy of the model. It is calculated as indicated in Eq. (7).

$$DSR = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (7)$$

2.5. Reference measurements for the metrological validation of the proposed methodology

Metrological validation is ensured through comparison with reference measurements for dimensional quantification of the detected defects obtained using a multisensor CMM ZEISS O-Inspect, shown in Fig. 9 (a). This system is equipped with three types of sensors: a tactile probe, an imaging sensor, and a chromatic confocal sensor. In this study, only the imaging sensor was used. The maximum permissible error (MPE) in 2D is $1.9 + L/150 \mu\text{m}$, where L is the length expressed in mm, as reported by the manufacturer according to ISO 10360-7:2011 [40]. A dimensional tolerance of $600 \mu\text{m}$ was set as the limit beyond which any detected protrusion is deemed non-conforming, and the part should be rejected.

To ensure reproducibility, the components were clamped using a simple yet effective fixturing system as shown in Fig. 9(b) and (c). As the part is symmetric, two alignment strategies (1 in Figs. 9(b) and 2 in Fig. 9(c)) were developed to inspect the defects present in the four lateral faces of the component: all defects on the first pair of mirrored faces were measured first; the part was then rotated, re-fixtured using the same clamping strategy, and the remaining two faces were measured (Fig. 9(c)). For each alignment, three reference planes, indicated as

Plane 1 – top (XY), Plane 2 – vertical (XZ), and Plane 3 – lateral (YZ), were first defined using contact measurements with the O-Inspect tactile probe; then, measurements with the imaging probing sensor were performed. The same naming convention per each component indicated in Section 2.1 and its lateral faces shown in Fig. 4(b) was maintained. Of all the scanned parts, approximately 20 % of those containing a defect were measured with the imaging sensor. As previously indicated, no other area such as the top and bottom surfaces of the part were analysed in this work.

Previous studies have applied different methods to determine the length of the detected burrs generated from micro-milling and drilling. For instance, Liang et al [41]. employed image-based and contour analysis methods to measure burr length or width in micro-milling applications. Others [42] introduced custom-made parameters to serve as descriptors of burr morphology; the measurement of the burrs area was compared against dimensional tolerances. In the context of drilling, Bahçe and Özdemir [43] compared multiple approaches to estimate average burr height, considering the burr area divided by the total length of the burr profile. The results were then subsequently compared to specified tolerances. In the proposed work, the dimensional measurement of the detected defects was performed by evaluating the maximum extension of the burrs, measured by manually selecting their two endpoints. More specifically, the measurements were performed as distances between two points using the “single point” measurement method available in the selected machine (examples of two defects found in components HSG-03–1 and HSG-13–1 are shown in Fig. 10). It is acknowledged that the chosen method is not highly robust or repeatable, due to the manual selection of endpoints, which clearly introduces a degree of subjectivity. Nevertheless, it was chosen to estimate the most critical condition, assuming that burrs may protrude or lift significantly from the surface. By considering the two endpoints of each burr, the maximum length was measured, offering a practical and conservative upper-bound estimate of its size, which was the primary objective of this evaluation. Each defect was measured five times, with a standard deviation s and a mean \bar{l} , as later reported in Table 4.

3. Results

The following sections present the results obtained from training and validating the DL model, followed by the outcomes of the defect detection and dimensional quantification phases. The model's performance is evaluated across multiple training configurations, and its predictions are compared with reference measurements to ensure traceability.

Fig. 9. Measurement set-up for dimensional quantification of defects: (a) ZEISS O-Inspect multisensor CMM, (b) and (c) fixturing strategy and datum-plane definition for lateral faces inspection (Alignments 1 and 2 respectively).

Fig. 10. Examples of burrs acquired with the ZEISS O-Inspect imaging sensor. The extension of the defects is calculated utilising the “single point” measurement method. The mean \bar{l} of five measurement repeats for the parts HSG-03-1 and HSG-13-1 is reported.

3.1. Training of the model and performance metrics

Five training trials were run exclusively on the images selected for training with a learning rate of 0.002 (i.e., the value that determines the step size during the optimisation process and affects how quickly and effectively a model learns. This parameter helps the model converge to a solution efficiently without getting stuck in local minima). This number was chosen in line with YOLOv8 online documentation, based on preliminary tests and the characteristics of the built-in optimiser, which benefits from moderately low learning rates to ensure stable convergence. The number of epochs (i.e., the number of iterations the model performs on the same dataset during the training phase) was set at 5, 10, 20, 50 and 100, to investigate how it influences the detection quality. In between each epoch, the fitted model was used to predict the responses for the observations in the validation subset. This was done by comparing the loss in both training and validation stages. Training loss is the metric that measures the model’s error on the training subset; it is computed after every batch (i.e., number of images processed simultaneously in a single network weight update operation) by summing the errors of the samples in that batch. On the other hand, validation loss measures the model’s error on the validation subset; it is calculated after each epoch by summing the errors over the entire validation images and indicates how well the model generalises to unseen data. If the validation loss fails to improve after a few consecutive epochs, best-performing model (i.e., the one corresponding to the epoch with the highest validation performance) is selected as the final configuration. Typically, the best model is identified based on the highest *mAP* on the validation set and is then evaluated on the test set to provide an unbiased estimate of its generalisation performance. When a model fitted to the training data achieves comparable performance on the test images, it signals that overfitting is minimal; the opposite is a clear warning of overfitting.

In this work, metrics were not evaluated at the last epoch, but rather at the epoch showing the best performance on the validation set. This choice allowed to compare different configurations of the model, and, at the same time, identify the optimal generalisation achieved during training. By selecting the best-performing results corresponding to the highest validation *mAP* the analysis avoids underestimating performance due to potential late-stage overfitting. The performance metrics (described in Section 2.3) evaluated at the best validation epoch for each training run are reported in Table 3.

The results showed that increasing the number of training epochs generally improves both *TPA* and *mAP*, with the highest *TPA* equal to 0.935 and *mAP* equal to 0.802 best achieved at 100 epochs. However, the *DSR* does not follow the same trend: it peaked at 50 epochs, reaching a score of 0.740, and then drastically dropped at 100 epochs (equal to 0.500), suggesting that although the model has become more accurate overall, it might have also become overly conservative, leading to more missed detections. The metric *TPR* reached its highest value at 50 epochs

Table 3

Performance metrics of the YOLOv8 model, changing the number of epochs. The results are reported at the best validation epoch for each training run.

Trial	Epochs	Training time	TPA	TPR	F Factor	DSR	mAP
1	5	11.9 min	0.475	0.700	0.566	0.400	0.604
2	10	46.8 min	0.664	0.791	0.722	0.460	0.763
3	20	69.7 min	0.714	0.750	0.732	0.555	0.744
4	50	116.3 min	0.788	0.800	0.784	0.740	0.832
5	100	285.4 min	0.935	0.725	0.817	0.500	0.802

and slightly decreased at 100 epochs, dropping from 0.800 to 0.725, as indication of a potential reduction in sensitivity to true positives when training is extensive. The highest *F Factor* was achieved at 100 epochs, reflecting the model’s ability to balance between precision (*TPA*) and recall (*TPR*) at that point. However, the drops in *TPR*, *DSR* and *mAP* values raised concerns related potential overfitting or increased selectivity in defect detection. For these reasons, although 100 epochs deliver the best individual scores in *TPA* and *F Factor*, the configuration with 50 training epochs offered the best overall compromise, delivering consistently high values across all metrics and combining strong detection performance with better generalisation.

3.2. Detection and quantification of defects

The best configuration of the model trained with 50 epochs was used to detect the imperfections on the dataset with unlabelled images. During the defect detection phase, the YOLOv8 model was first used to identify imperfections by generating bounding boxes around regions of interest. These bounding boxes were then used to estimate defect length by applying a pixel-to-millimetre conversion factor, as indicated in Section 2.3. It was found that for defects of length greater than 1.50–2 mm (measured using the imaging sensor), the bounding boxes generated by the model provided reasonably accurate size estimates, with an average deviation of about 0.30 mm compared to the reference measurements. In contrast, for smaller defects ranging from 0.80 to 1.50 mm the bounding boxes tended to overestimate, with deviations sometimes exceeding 0.50 mm. Due to these limitations, the quantification of the defects’ extension solely based on the calculation of the bounding box was paired with a skeletonization algorithm applied to the same images. The geometry of the skeleton path, obtained as described in Section 2.3, was converted into millimetres using the same conversion factor indicated in Eq. (1). For each component containing a defect, the system generated an annotated image with both the bounding box and its dimension, and the defect length estimate derived from the skeleton analysis. An example result of the application of these two strategies can be found in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Detected defect in HSG-05-1, (a) acquired with the imaging sensor and measured with the single point distance tool, (b) identified with the bounding box generated by the DL-model, and (c) measured the bounding box paired with skeletonization.

3.3. Comparison with reference measurements

A comparison between the lengths of the defects measured using the imaging sensor mounted in the multisensor CMM and those estimated by the YOLOv8 skeleton algorithm was performed. As noted in Section 2.4, out of all the scanned components that exhibited defects, approximately 20 % were further examined using the imaging sensor. Again, top and bottom surfaces were not included in the analysis. For each defect, five measurements were taken, and the mean value \bar{l} , the standard deviation s , and the corresponding skeleton-based estimate L_{sk} were recorded. The results of the comparison are reported in Table 4.

The average deviation between the two measurement methods was found to be 0.294 mm, with a maximum deviation of 0.607 mm observed for HSG-13-1 and a minimum deviation of 0.144 mm observed for HSG-17-1. The variability observed in L_{sk} can be attributed to the quality of the input images generated from the deviation maps, which in turn depends on the quality of the measured point clouds. In some cases, such as HSG-06-1, HSG-07-1, and HSG-09-1, the defect was not detected by the algorithm, and thus no comparison could be made. It is likely that the measurements obtained with the AACMM laser-based sensor did not exhibit a sufficient resolution to clearly capture the geometry and size of the defect, leading to missed detections by the CNN

and the consequent absence of corresponding comparative data. Furthermore, it was observed in some cases that the skeletonization algorithm resulted in larger estimations of defect size compared to those obtained from the multisensor CMM, suggesting a tendency to slightly overestimate the defect extension. This generally occurred for defects smaller than 1 mm. On the contrary, the algorithm appeared to be more conservative in the case of larger defects. While such overestimation may reduce measurement accuracy, it can be seen as beneficial in the context of automated in-line inspection, where the early detection of potentially critical defects is often prioritised over strict metrological performances. Examples of this comparison are shown in Fig. 12.

4. Discussion

The following discussion analyses the model’s predictive performance and its ability to detect and quantify defects, providing their dimensional estimates, which have been then compared to a reference. In addition, the practical limitations observed during the experiments, with particular attention to defect size variability, and implications for in-line industrial applications will be identified.

The metrics chosen to investigate the performance of the proposed CNN were selected to quantify the model’s ability to reliably localise

Table 4

Comparison between repeated measurements obtained with imaging sensor and output of the skeletonization algorithm. The results are expressed in mm.

	l_1	l_2	l_3	l_4	l_5	\bar{l}	s	L_{sk}	Deviation
HSG-01-1	0.915	0.912	0.918	0.915	0.918	0.916	0.002	1.300	0.384
HSG-02-1	0.712	0.709	0.682	0.709	0.758	0.714	0.028	0.900	0.186
HSG-03-1	1.124	1.117	1.106	1.112	1.121	1.116	0.007	0.700	- 0.416
HSG-04-1	1.619	1.665	1.596	1.621	1.604	1.621	0.027	1.400	- 0.221
HSG-05-1	1.518	1.533	1.530	1.509	1.525	1.523	0.010	1.700	0.177
HSG-06-1	2.064	2.079	2.069	2.113	2.123	2.090	0.027	Not detected	/
HSG-07-1	0.395	0.399	0.393	0.390	0.405	0.396	0.006	Not detected	/
HSG-07-2	0.774	0.787	0.775	0.810	0.789	0.787	0.015	1.000	0.213
HSG-08-1	0.741	0.742	0.743	0.866	0.743	0.767	0.056	1.000	0.233
HSG-09-1	1.507	1.492	1.531	1.540	1.518	1.518	0.019	Not detected	/
HSG-10-1	1.162	1.136	1.138	1.155	1.156	1.149	0.012	1.400	0.251
HSG-11-1	0.495	0.434	0.435	0.460	0.485	0.462	0.028	Not detected	/
HSG-12-1	1.600	1.595	1.592	1.637	1.493	1.583	0.054	1.300	- 0.283
HSG-13-1	0.784	0.738	0.787	0.776	0.879	0.793	0.052	1.400	0.607
HSG-14-1	1.088	1.175	1.161	1.109	1.078	1.122	0.044	Not detected	/
HSG-14-2	2.100	2.109	2.103	2.068	2.076	2.091	0.018	1.800	- 0.291
HSG-15-1	0.705	0.678	0.673	0.661	0.661	0.676	0.018	Not detected	/
HSG-16-1	3.201	3.183	3.138	3.194	3.186	3.180	0.025	2.800	- 0.380
HSG-17-1	2.295	2.366	1.893	2.451	2.775	2.356	0.318	2.500	0.144
HSG-18-1	1.925	2.069	2.124	2.140	2.102	2.072	0.086	1.600	- 0.472
HSG-19-1	2.332	2.311	2.256	1.935	1.950	2.157	0.198	2.000	- 0.157

Fig. 12. Examples of measured and DL-detected lengths for three components (HSG-01-1, HSG-04-1 and HSG-18-1 respectively): (a) imaging (single point measurement), and (b) DL-driven skeletonization algorithm.

defects in the images and minimise the number of false positives. In addition, in real scenarios, the substantial presence of false negatives is particularly critical, especially in quality control applications: undetected defects can lead to faulty products reaching customers or proceeding to downstream processes. As reported in Section 3, the model trained for 50 epochs provided the best compromise across all metrics, with a *TPA* of 0.788, *TPR* of 0.800, and a peak *DSR* of 0.740, indicating balanced performance with good generalisation. In contrast, training for 100 epochs, although yielding the highest *TPA* of 0.935 and *F Factor* of 0.817, led to a significant drop in *DSR* and raised concerns of potential overfitting. Specifically, *TPA* was used to assess the reliability of positive predictions and reduce false detections, whereas *TPR* ensured that true defects were consistently detected. High *TPA* values are related to low false positive rates, while high *TPR* values can be linked to low false negative rates. The *F Factor* is a summary metric, able to capture the balance between the latter and the former. In an ideal case, it should be equal to 1. The *mAP* was also considered, as it combines both classification performance and localisation accuracy into a single metric, providing a complete measure of the model's detection capabilities. Unlike other metrics that simply evaluated whether a defect was detected, *mAP* also accounted for how precisely the predicted location of the defect overlapped with its real location. For this reason, *mAP* is particularly valuable in object detection tasks, where accurate localisation is as important as correct classification. The *mAP* for 50 epochs scored the highest result (equal to 0.832). It is important to point out that metrics like *TPA* and *TPR* are more suitable for object detection tasks than *DSR* metric. The latter is not particularly informative in this context [44], due to several reasons. First, many images may not contain any defect, making true negatives difficult to be interpreted. Second, object detection models like YOLOv8 can predict both classification and location, and a prediction that is correct in class but incorrect in position will still be considered as false positive. More specifically, in unbalanced datasets where non-defective images are predominant, a model that simply avoids predicting any defect can still achieve a high *DSR*, while being useless for its initial purpose. Nevertheless, a measure of *DSR* was given for each trial. Although the sample size of images used for training the DL model is limited by the number of available components (92 parts generating 368 deviation maps, later balanced to 85/75 originals), the fine-tuned YOLOv8 achieved balanced performance at 50 epochs, supporting the proof-of-concept scope of this study. To mirror in-line variability, data augmentation was applied using controlled perturbations (i. e., exposure $\pm 10\%$, brightness $\pm 15\%$, saturation $\pm 15\%$, rotation $\pm 5^\circ$) to avoid unrealistic artefacts. The performance peaked at 50

epochs and degradation at 100 epochs suggested that, within these realistic ranges, augmentation did not induce overfitting and remained appropriate for the target inspection scenario.

From the analysis of the detected defects, a limitation in the sole use of the bounding box related to the defect size estimation has been observed. While acceptable approximations were obtained for defects around and above 2 mm length, the bounding box method consistently overestimated the size of smaller defects. First, this is likely due to an approximation of the rectangular enclosure to irregular and complex defect morphologies. Second, this result is potentially linked to the performance of the model and the limited number of small-defect samples in the training image dataset. Furthermore, as previously pointed out, the resolution of the point clouds may not be sufficient to accurately represent complex defect edges, particularly in the case of defects featuring indented shapes. On the contrary, the skeletonization algorithm paired with the bounding box computation provided a good agreement with the length estimates obtained with the imaging sensor, especially for defects with elongated shapes. Its ability to trace internal features enabled more realistic estimations of the defect extension. However, this method is still sensitive to two factors: first, the quality of the deviation maps that can alter the extracted skeleton and thus the length estimate; second, the image adaptation required by the detector: resizing to 640×640 pixels without padding entails non-uniform scaling whenever the original aspect ratio is not square, which may distort the geometry of the defects. Lengths are nevertheless computed in millimetres after skeletonization using a conversion factor, which controls the global scale; a residual axis-dependent anisotropy may remain. On our dataset, for defects typically ranging from approx. 0.7–3 mm (Table 4), the multisensor CMM comparison reports a mean absolute deviation of 0.294 mm and no clear size-dependent trend, suggesting no relevant systematic bias from resizing under our conditions. Despite these limitations, both approaches demonstrated sufficient robustness for practical use in potential in-line defect detection scenarios. The comparison to reference measurements enables the evaluation of the robustness of ML-based tools in relation to traditional metrological solutions, despite inherent limitations. The variability observed in the deviation between the imaging measurements and the skeletonization results stems primarily from the quality of the point clouds and the consequent resolution of the deviation maps used to generate the images for training, evaluating and testing the model. As previously mentioned, in correspondence to some defects (specifically HSG-06-1, HSG-07-1, HSG-09-1, HSG-11-1, HSG-14-1, HSG-15-1), the quality of the scan likely limited the ability of the model to spot such defects, resulting in missed detections. It is important to note that no

clear correlation was found between defect size and deviation to the reference. Generally speaking, defects exhibited deviations typically below or slightly above 0.50 mm. It is worth noting that the reference lengths obtained with the imaging sensor are determined as straight lines between two manually chosen endpoints. This is comparable to the skeleton centrelines only in case of elongated defects with simple geometries. For complex or branched defects, the straight line is usually shorter than the centreline, so the skeletonization algorithm likely overestimates the length of such imperfections. In addition, different endpoint choices in the reference measurements add variability, especially in the case of defects with complex shapes. As a result, defects that spread laterally (e.g., burrs in correspondence of the joints) are emphasised and are detected more reliably, whereas spike-like protrusions presenting small lateral descriptors and large height excursions are missed. Consequently, the reported measurements refer to the in-plane extent of each anomaly, whereas height is not quantified.

The pipeline is conceived for direct integration in an in-line inspection cell: (i) the component geometry is acquired by means of optical measurement, (ii) each side is registered to a defect-free master and converted into a deviation map; (iii) YOLOv8 performs defect localisation on the images generated from the deviation maps; (iv) the defect mask is skeletonized to estimate length and converted to metric units via a pixel-to-mm factor; (v) defects exceeding a predefined tolerance are flagged for rejection; (vi) images, predictions, dimensional estimates, and decisions are logged for tracking. The proposed approach may represent a viable support tool for in-line inspection not only in die-casting, but also in other manufacturing processes potentially generating surface defects. Its integration within quality control frameworks could aid in defect detection at early stages, especially in cases where conventional metrological systems are not feasible due to speed or integration constraints.

5. Conclusion

This study presented a metrologically validated pipeline for the automated detection and dimensional quantification of surface defects on die-cast components. The proposed method combined a DL-based approach applied to deviation maps with a skeletonization algorithm for length measurements. The pipeline was trained and evaluated on a dataset of processed images obtained from point clouds acquired through a laser-based sensor. This data was then compared to a higher-resolution reference scan obtained from a previously developed in-line optical setup. To validate the DL-based procedure, reference dimensional measurements were performed using a multisensor CMM equipped with an imaging sensor. The DL model employed, based on the YOLOv8 architecture, achieved balanced detection performance and demonstrated robust capabilities in identifying and localising surface imperfections across a variety of conditions. To first evaluate the approximate dimensions of the detected defects, the use of bounding boxes provided an initial estimation; then, the incorporation of the skeletonization algorithm led to a significantly improved dimensional assessments, especially in the case of elongated or irregularly shaped defects. A direct comparison with imaging sensor measurements showed an average deviation of 0.294 mm, confirming the pipeline's potential for practical application in in-line inspection workflows. Such average deviation can be further reduced by using data from laser sensors with higher accuracy than the one available for the current study and adopting aspect-ratio-preserving letterboxing (i.e., no warping) at the image resizing stage. Overall, the study should be interpreted as a proof-of-concept under realistic constraints of part availability and acquisition resolution, with industrial deployments expected to provide larger and more diverse data for further scaling.

From an industrial perspective, the results suggest that the proposed pipeline may be integrated as a support tool to human visual inspection in hybrid quality control systems for die-casting and other high-volume manufacturing processes, where surface defects must be identified and

characterised rapidly. While current limitations include sensitivity to point cloud resolution, manual image processing, and limited robustness for sub-millimetre defects, the overall performance is promising. Future developments of this study should focus on enhancing the robustness and scalability of the proposed pipeline across a broader range of industrial conditions. First, expanding the dataset with additional components, defect types, and surface finishes is essential to improve the generalisation capabilities of the model and reduce the risk of overfitting. In particular, the inclusion of more samples with small or complex defects could significantly increase the model's sensitivity and classification accuracy. The proposed pipeline is conceived as process-agnostic, since it operates on 3D deviation maps derived from dense point clouds and relies on a skeletonization-based quantification of the defect mask; this representation is not tied to a specific process and can, in principle, accommodate different defect footprints, provided that the anomalies exhibit a predominantly in-plane 3D morphology, with spike-like protrusions remaining more challenging at this stage. What remains process-dependent are the statistics and visual appearance of the defects in the deviation maps, so that extending the approach beyond the die casting case study will require collecting representative, labelled datasets for each target process and re-training or fine-tuning the CNN accordingly. Another promising direction is the integration of active learning strategies, whereby the network could iteratively improve by incorporating newly acquired images, potentially captured in-line. This would enable a refinement of performance with minimal manual intervention, supporting continuous learning in real production environments. Then, the acquisition of data storing labelled defects represents a valuable opportunity to build an archive of the detected defects over time. Studying their evolution could be used to correlate the occurrence of specific surface imperfections with changes in production parameters, wear, or other external factors, supporting predictive quality control strategies and long-term process optimisation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sofia Catalucci: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Enrico Savio:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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